

ANNEX 1: NBS CLASSIFICATION SCHEME

Type 1 - Better use of protected/natural ecosystems - No or minimal intervention in ecosystems, with the objectives of maintaining or improving the delivery of a range of ES both inside and outside of these preserved ecosystems

Protection and conservation strategies in terrestrial (e.g. Natura2000), marine (e.g. MPA), and coastal areas (e.g. mangroves) ecosystems

- Limit or prevent specific uses and practices
- Ensure continuity with ecological network
- Protect forests from clearing and degradation from logging, fire, and unsustainable levels of non-timber resource extraction
- Maintain and enhance natural wetlands
- Protect remaining intertidal muds, saltmarshes and mangrove communities, seagrass beds, and vegetated dunes from further degradation, fragmentation, and loss.
- Natural Protected Area network structure
- Mangrove forests protected area MPA network structure

Type 2 - NBS for sustainability and multifunctionality of managed ecosystems - Definition and implementation of management approaches that develop sustainable and multifunctional ecosystems and landscapes (extensively or intensively managed), which improves the delivery of selected ES compared to what would be obtained with a more conventional intervention

Agricultural landscape management

- Agro-ecological practices
- Use grazing management and animal impact as farm and ecosystem development tools
- Change crop rotations
- Soil improvement and conservation measures
- Increase soil water holding capacity and infiltration rates
- Agro-ecological network structure
- Mulching
- Incorporating manure, compost, biosolids, or incorporating crop residues to enhance carbon storage
- Integrate biochar into agricultural soils

- Enrichment planting in degraded and regenerating forests
- Forest patches
- Hedge and planted fence
- Flower strips
- Cover crops
- Wind breaks
- Deep-rooted plants and minimum or conservation tillage
- Agroforestry

Coastal landscape management

- Encourage development of early successional sand dune habitats (dry dunes and wet slacks) where carbon sequestration rates are high.
- Enhance or facilitate habitat expansion, including the facilitated range expansion of mangroves, as warming conditions and changes in storm occurrence permit.
- Integrated coastal zone management

Extensive urban green space management

- Ensure continuity with ecological network
- Planning tools to control urban expansion
- Historical urban green network structure
- Choices of plants
- Heritage park
- Urban natural protected areas
- Introduced vs. local plants
- Vegetation diversification
- Green corridors and belts
- Planning tools for biodiversity, green infrastructure, and ecosystem services
- Tools to engage citizens
- Mapping green features

Monitoring

- Assessment of NBS benefits
- Ecosystem services valuation methods
- Bio-indicators

Type 3 - Design and management of new ecosystems - Managing ecosystems in very intrusive ways or even creating new ecosystems (e.g., artificial ecosystems with new assemblages of organisms for green roofs and walls to mitigate city warming and clean polluted air).

Intensive urban green space management

- Integrated pest management
- Integrated weed management
- Integrated and ecological management - spatial aspects
- Integrated and ecological management - time and frequency aspects
- Create and preserve habitats and shelters for biodiversity
- Choices of plants
- Large urban park
- Pocket garden/park
- Community garden
- Green cemetery
- Hedge and planted fence
- Private garden
- Urban forest
- Flower field
- Street trees
- Intensive green roof
- Semi-intensive green roof
- Extensive green roof
- Roof Pond
- Climber green wall
- Green wall system
- Planter green wall
- Vegetable garden
- Urban orchards
- Urban vineyards
- Meadow

- Urban farm
- Introduced vs. local plants
- Vegetation diversification
- Plant and bio-filter features
- Moss green roofs
- Urban network structures

Urban planning strategies

- Direct human intervention
- Use of fauna
- Account for distribution of public green spaces through the city
- Planning tools for climate change adaptation/mitigation and ecosystem services
- Mapping of urban green connectivity and biodiversity

Urban water management

- Develop urban blue infrastructure
- Streams, including re-meandering, re-opening Blue corridors
- Sustainable Urban Drainage Systems
- Integrated water management

Ecological restoration of degraded terrestrial ecosystems

- Quarry restoration
- Phytoremediation
- Systems for erosion control
- Soil and slope revegetation
- Strong slope revegetation
- Replace hard engineered river stabilisation with softer alternatives (e.g. willow-based)
- Plant trees/ hedges/perennial grass strips to intercept surface run-off
- Use of pre-existing vegetation

Restoration and creation of semi-natural water bodies and hydrographic networks

- Restore wetlands in areas of groundwater recharge
- Reconnect rivers with floodplains to enhance natural water storage
- Re-vegetation of riverbanks
- Re-meander rivers (where they have been artificially straightened) to help reduce speed and height of flood peaks
- Restore grassland/low input arable in drinking water catchments
- Use engineered reedbeds/wetlands for tertiary treatment of effluent
- Target ponds/wetland creation to trap sediment/pollution runoff in farmed landscape
- Constructed wetlands and built structures for water management
- Rivers or streams, including re-meandering, re-opening Blue corridors
- Floodplain restoration and management
- Reshape river and riverbanks in urban areas

Ecological restoration of degraded coastal and marine ecosystems

- Create new intertidal habitat through afforestation, or planting of saltmarsh or seagrass at appropriate elevations in the tidal frame
- Restore micro-topography, creek networks, sediment inputs, and nutrient exchange in abandoned aquaculture ponds.
- Re-establish and restore previous intertidal habitat by de-poldering or coastal realignment
- Ecological restoration of degraded coastal and marine ecosystems
- Coastal sand engine
- Dune replenishment

ANNEX 2: NBS APPROACHES, CHALLENGES, AND ECOSYSTEM SERVICES PER TYPE

Food, crops, wild foods, and spices (F)	Carbon sequestration and climate regulation. (CS&R)	Nutrient dispersal & and cycling (N)	Recreation (R)
Water (W)	Water purification (WP)	Seed dispersal (SD)	Intellectual and aesthetic appreciation (I)
Pharmaceuticals, biochemicals, and industry. Products (P)	Air quality regulation (AQ)	Soil formation and composting (SFC)	Spiritual and symbolic appreciation (S)
Energy (E)	Erosion prevention (EP)	Primary production (P)	
	Flood protection (FP)		
	Maintaining populations and habitats (MP&H)		
	Pest and disease control (P&DC)		
	Crop pollination (CP)		

NBS TYPES		🔍 NBS APPROACH											
		Climate adaptation approaches	Community based adaptation	Ecosystem based adaptation	Ecosystem based management	Ecosystem based mitigation	Ecosystem based disaster risk reduction	Ecological engineering	Ecological restoration	Infrastructure related approaches	Natural resources management	Sustainable agriculture/agro-forestry/aquaculture	
Type 1: Better use of protected/natural ecosystems Sustainable agriculture/agro-forestry/aquaculture													
Protection and conservation strategies	Limit or prevent specific uses and practices				X						X		
	Protect forests from clearing and degradation from logging, fire, and unsustainable levels of non-timber resource extraction	X	X		X	X	X		X	X	X	X	
	Maintain and enhance natural wetlands			X	X				X				
	Protect remaining intertidal muds, saltmarshes and mangrove communities, seagrass beds, and vegetated dunes from further degradation, fragmentation, and loss.	X											
	MPA network structure			X	X	X	X		X	X			

NBS CHALLENGES										ECOSYSTEM SERVICES		
Climate mitigation and adaptation	Water management	Coastal resilience	Green space management	Air quality	Urban regeneration	Participatory planning and governance	Social justice and social cohesion	Public health and wellbeing	Potential of economic opportunities and green jobs	Provisioning services: (F), (W), (P), (E) *	Regulation and maintenance: (CS&R), (WP), (AQ), (EP), (FP), (MP&H), (P&DC), (CP)*	Cultural: (R), (I), (S)*
X	X		X	X	X		X	X		(W)	(AQ), (EP), (FP), (CS&R)	(R), (I)
X						X	X		X		(EP), (FP), (MP&H), (CS&R)	
X	X	X				X			X	(W), (F)	(WP), (FP), (MP&H)	(R), (I)
		X	X							(F)	(FP), (MP&H)	(R), (I)
	X	X						X				(R), (I)

NBS TYPES		🔍 NBS APPROACH									
		Climate adaptation approaches	Community based adaptation	Ecosystem based adaptation	Ecosystem based management	Ecosystem based mitigation	Ecosystem based disaster risk reduction	Ecological engineering	Ecological restoration	Infrastructure related approaches	Natural resources management
Type 2: NBS for sustainability and multifunctionality of managed ecosystems											
Agricultural landscape management	Agro-ecological practices	X			X		X		X		
	Use grazing management and animal impact as farm and ecosystem development tools				X						
	Change crop rotations				X						
	Soil improvement and conservation measures				X						
	Increase soil water holding capacity and infiltration rates		X	X	X		X		X		
	Incorporating manure, compost, biosolids, or incorporating crop residues to enhance carbon storage				X						X
	Enrichment planting in degraded and regenerating forests	X			X						
	Forest patches	X			X						
	Deep-rooted plants and minimum or conservation tillage				X					X	
	Agroforestry	X									

	NBS CHALLENGES										ECOSYSTEM SERVICES		
Sustainable agriculture/agro-forestry/aquaculture	Climate mitigation and adaptation	Water management	Coastal resilience	Green space management	Air quality	Urban regeneration	Participatory planning and governance	Social justice and social cohesion	Public health and wellbeing	Potential of economic opportunities and green jobs	Provisioning services: (F), (W), (P), (E) *	Regulation and maintenance: (CS&R), (WP), (AQ), (EP), (FP), (MP&H), (P&DC), (CP)*	Cultural: (R), (I), (S)*
X	X	X					X	X		X	(W), (F)	(AQ), (CS&R), (WP), (FP)	(R), (I)
X							X	X		X		(MP & H)	(I)
X		X					X	X		X	(W)	(WP)	
X		X					X	X	X	X		(WP), (EP), (CS&R)	(I)
X		X					X	X	X	X	(W)	(FP)	
		X									(W)	(MP&H)	(I), (S)
X	X	X			X		X	X				(MP&H), (CS&R)	(R), (I)
X							X	X				(MP&H), (CS&R)	(R), (I)
X								X		X		(MP&H),	(R), (I)
X	X											(MP&H), (CS&R)	(R), (I)

NBS TYPES		NBS APPROACH									
		Climate adaptation approaches	Community based adaptation	Ecosystem based adaptation	Ecosystem based management	Ecosystem based mitigation	Ecosystem based disaster risk reduction	Ecological engineering	Ecological restoration	Infrastructure related approaches	Natural resources management
Type 2: NBS for sustainability and multifunctionality of managed ecosystems											
Coastal landscape management	Integrated coastal zone management	X			X		X		X		
Extensive urban green space management	Ensure continuity with ecological network	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Planning tools to control urban expansion	X		X	X					X	
	Planning tools for biodiversity, green infrastructure, and ecosystem services	X	X	X	X				X		
	Heritage park		X		X						
	Green belt	X		X		X	X				
	Tools to engage citizens		X	X	X			X		X	
Monitoring	Assessment of NBS benefits	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X
	Ecosystem services valuation methods				X						
	Bio-indicators	X									

	NBS CHALLENGES										ECOSYSTEM SERVICES		
Sustainable agriculture/agro-forestry/aquaculture	Climate mitigation and adaptation	Water management	Coastal resilience	Green space management	Air quality	Urban regeneration	Participatory planning and governance	Social justice and social cohesion	Public health and wellbeing	Potential of economic opportunities and green jobs	Provisioning services: (F), (W), (P), (E) *	Regulation and maintenance: (CS&R), (WP), (AQ), (EP), (FP), (MP&H), (P&DC), (CP)*	Cultural: (R), (I), (S)*
X	X	X					X	X		X	(W), (F)	(AQ), (CS&R), (WP), (FP)	(R), (I)
	X	X		X	X	X		X	X		(W)	(CS&R), (WP), (AQ), (FP), (MP&H)	(R), (I)
	X	X		X	X	X		X	X		(F)	(AQ), (FP), (MP&H)	(R), (I)
X	X		X			X	X	X		X		(FP), (MP&H)	(I)
X	X	X		X	X	X		X	X			(MP&H)	(R), (S)
	X	X		X	X			X	X			(AQ), (FP), (CS&R)	(R)
	X			X		X	X	X	X	X			(R), (I)
X	X	X	X	X			X		X		(W)	(FP), (MP&H), (EP)	(I)
		X					X		X				(I)
	X			X	X				X	X	(P)	(MP&H)	(R), (I)

NBS TYPES		🔍 NBS APPROACH									
		Climate adaptation approaches	Community based adaptation	Ecosystem based adaptation	Ecosystem based management	Ecosystem based mitigation	Ecosystem based disaster risk reduction	Ecological engineering	Ecological restoration	Infrastructure related approaches	Natural resources management
Type 3: Design and management of new ecosystems											
Intensive urban green space management	Integrated and ecological management - spatial aspects	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X
	Create and preserve habitats and shelters for biodiversity		X						X		
	Choices of plants							X	X	X	
	Large urban park	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X
	Pocket garden/park		X		X	X					
	Community garden	X	X		X	X				X	
	Private garden	X					X				
	Urban forest	X								X	
	Street trees				X	X				X	
	Intensive green roof/ Semi-intensive green roof/ Extensive green roof	X			X				X	X	
	Climber green wall	X								X	
	Green wall system	X							X	X	
	Planter green wall								X		X
	Vegetable garden		X		X	X					
	Urban orchards										
Urban network structures								X	X	X	

NBS CHALLENGES												ECOSYSTEM SERVICES		
Sustainable agriculture/agro-forestry/aquaculture	Climate mitigation and adaptation	Water management	Coastal resilience	Green space management	Air quality	Urban regeneration	Participatory planning and governance	Social justice and social cohesion	Public health and wellbeing	Potential of economic opportunities and green jobs	Provisioning services: (F), (W), (P), (E) *	Regulation and maintenance: (CS&R), (WP), (AQ), (EP), (FP), (MP&H), (P&DC), (CP)*	Cultural: (R), (I), (S)*	
	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X		(W)	(AQ), (FP), (MP&H), (CS&R), (WP)	(R), (I), (S)	
X		X		X	X				X		(E)	(AQ), (FP), (MP&H), (CS&R)	(R), (I), (S)	
	X	X											(I),	
	X	X		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	(P), (E)	(AQ), (FP), (MP&H), (EP), (CS&R), (WP)	(R), (I), (S)	
	X	X		X	X	X		X	X		(E)	(AQ), (FP), (MP&H), (CS&R)	(R), (I), (S)	
X	X	X		X	X	X		X	X		(E)	(AQ), (FP), (MP&H), (CS&R)	(R), (I), (S)	
	X	X		X	X	X	X	X	X			(WP), (AQ), (FP), (CS&R)	(R), (I)	
	X	X			X				X		(P)	(AQ), (CS&R),	(R), (I)	
	X								X			(AQ), (CS&R),		
	X	X		X	X	X		X	X		(W)	(AQ), (FP), (CS&R), (WP)	(R), (I)	
	X			X	X	X		X	X			(AQ), (CS&R),	(R), (I)	
	X			X	X	X			X			(MP&H), (CS&R)	(I)	
									X			(AQ)	(I)	
X		X		X		X		X	X		(E)	(MP&H), (CS&R)	(R), (I), (S)	
X		X		X	X	X		X	X		(F), (E)			
									X			(MP&H), (CS&R)	(R), (I)	

NBS TYPES		🔍 NBS APPROACH									
		Climate adaptation approaches	Community based adaptation	Ecosystem based adaptation	Ecosystem based management	Ecosystem based mitigation	Ecosystem based disaster risk reduction	Ecological engineering	Ecological restoration	Infrastructure related approaches	Natural resources management
Type 3: Design and management of new ecosystems											
Urban planning strategies	Use of fauna		X		X	X					
	Account for distribution of public green spaces through the city	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X
	Mapping of urban green connectivity and biodiversity	X	X	X	X	X	X				
Urban water management	Develop urban blue infrastructure	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X	
	Sustainable Urban Drainage Systems	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	
	Integrated water management	X									X
Ecological restoration of degraded terrestrial ecosystems	Systems for erosion control				X		X		X		X
	Use of pre-existing vegetation	X		X	X	X	X		X		X

	NBS CHALLENGES										ECOSYSTEM SERVICES		
Sustainable agriculture/agro-forestry/aquaculture	Climate mitigation and adaptation	Water management	Coastal resilience	Green space management	Air quality	Urban regeneration	Participatory planning and governance	Social justice and social cohesion	Public health and wellbeing	Potential of economic opportunities and green jobs	Provisioning services: (F), (W), (P), (E) *	Regulation and maintenance: (CS&R), (WP), (AQ), (EP), (FP), (MP&H), (P&DC), (CP)*	Cultural: (R), (I), (S)*
X		X		X		X		X			(E)	(MP&H), (CS&R)	(R), (S)
		X		X	X	X	X	X	X			(AQ), (MP&H), (CS&R), (FP)	(R), (I), (S)
	X			X	X	X	X	X	X	X	(W)	(WP), (AQ), (CS&R), (FP)	(I)
	X								X		(W), (E)	(WP), (AQ), (FP), (MP&H)	(R), (I)
		X		X	X	X		X	X		(W)	(CS&R), (WP), (AQ), (FP), (MP&H)	(R), (I)
		X		X	X	X		X		X	(W)	(CS&R), (WP), (FP)	(R)
	X	X		X							(W)	(CS&R), (WP), (EP), (AQ), (FP), (MP&H)	(R), (I)
		X		X	X	X		X	X		(W)	(WP), (AQ), (EP), (FP), (CS&R)	(R), (I)

NBS TYPES		🔍 NBS APPROACH									
		Climate adaptation approaches	Community based adaptation	Ecosystem based adaptation	Ecosystem based management	Ecosystem based mitigation	Ecosystem based disaster risk reduction	Ecological engineering	Ecological restoration	Infrastructure related approaches	Natural resources management
Type 3: Design and management of new ecosystems											
Restoration and creation of semi-natural water bodies and hydrographic networks	Re-meander rivers (where they have been artificially straightened) to help reduce speed and height of flood peaks	X		X	X	X	X	X	X		X
	Use engineered reedbeds/wetlands for tertiary treatment of effluent					X	X	X	X	X	
	Constructed wetlands and built structures for water management			X	X				X		
	Rivers or streams, including re-meandering, re-opening Blue corridors				X			X	X	X	X
Ecological restoration of degraded coastal and marine ecosystems	Re-establish and restore previous intertidal habitat by de-poldering or coastal realignment	X		X	X		X	X	X		X

	NBS CHALLENGES										ECOSYSTEM SERVICES		
Sustainable agriculture/agro-forestry/aquaculture	Climate mitigation and adaptation	Water management	Coastal resilience	Green space management	Air quality	Urban regeneration	Participatory planning and governance	Social justice and social cohesion	Public health and wellbeing	Potential of economic opportunities and green jobs	Provisioning services: (F), (W), (P), (E) *	Regulation and maintenance: (CS&R), (WP), (AQ), (EP), (FP), (MP&H), (P&DC), (CP)*	Cultural: (R), (I), (S)*
	X	X		X	X	X		X	X		(W)	(FP)	(R), (I)
		X							X		(W)	(WP), (FP), (MP&H)	(R), (I)
		X				X			X		(W), (E)	(WP), (MP&H)	(R), (I)
X		X		X	X			X	X		(F)	(WP), (FP), (MP&H), (CS&R), (EP)	(R), (I)
X	X		X	X	X			X			(F), (W)	(EP), (FP), (CS&R), (MP&H)	(R), (I)